

FEATURES OF MEDICAL EDUCATION AND THE ROLE OF THE UNIVERSITY TEACHER IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS AT THE PRESENT STAGE

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In the 90s of the last century, the world educational community rethought not only the concept of "education", but also other related terms, such as "training". The term "education" began to be replaced by the term "learning". In the first case, the main figure in the educational process was the teacher, "a guide leading to knowledge, skills and abilities." In the second one, the central figure becomes the one "who himself goes to knowledge-skills-skills", more precisely, "to the formation of his own personal culture" [11].

Since 1996 of the last century, in the used documents related to the quality of education, the term "competence" has appeared (it is impossible to teach, you can only learn), i.e. The essence of education is self-education. Everything else is just factors, resources and conditions that contribute to or hinder the normal development of the process of self-education. For the Russian educational community, this turn to self-education is not something new, because our compatriot P.F. Kanterev in 1885. Thus, taking into account what has been said, L.S. Grebnev in 2011 proposed the formulation of education at the present stage. "Education is a process of self-change of a person, as a result of which he masters new (for himself) knowledge, skills, abilities and competencies ...". Competence is a characteristic of the requirements for a person that will allow him to become competent in a certain type of activity. Competence is the ability, based on the organic unity of knowledge, skills and experience, to carry out both usual and new professional activities [3, 11, 16, 21, 29].

When entering the European and world educational space, there is a very important condition - the preservation of domestic educational traditions. In 2003, the Russian Federation signed the Bologna Declaration. The main directions of the Bologna Declaration coincide with the plans to reform the education system in Russia. Much attention is paid to the efficiency and quality of training specialists. Unfortunately, at present, the development of the medical education system is taking on painful forms, since it is not about education, but about an educational service, in accordance with the Law "On Education" (2012) [32, 35].

According to A.K. Subbetto, a university can be considered a system consisting of elements that include pedagogical, research components, as well as economic, social components, and according to L.S. Grebnev, a control system should be added here. Educational activity in the structure of the pedagogical system is the leading one, during which services are provided within the framework of basic and additional (postgraduate) education with the release of educational and methodological products. In the research system, the leading activity is scientific activity, the result of which is scientific and technical products produced at the university. The interaction of these two systems ensures the formation of an integrated product, including innovative developments and educational services [11, 12, 34].

The education paradigm is changing. Now it is no longer a person who is taught, but a person who learns. The logic of education is aimed at the independent work of the individual, where she (the individual) moves to a new level of creative development. Formation of the paradigm of education with a focus on the criteria of the Bologna process imposes new requirements on the quality of the educational system, the development of professional competence of the individual [6]. Competence is defined as a person's possession of the appropriate competence, including his personal attitude to it and the subject of activity, understanding of responsibility for his actions. The competency-based approach in education laid the foundation for the formation of modular disciplines that form a group of related competencies that ensure the formation of a specialist capable of building knowledge in accordance with new conditions [36]

J. Raven [28] considers the components of competence to be those "characteristics and abilities of people that allow them to achieve personally significant goals. These components of competence are divided into cognitive (determining obstacles to achieving goals), affective (pleasure from work) and volitional (perseverance, determination, will). The development of new skills, abilities and types of competence occurs depending on the goals that are significant for the individual at the present time.

Modern consumers of educational services evaluate the quality of education and the preparedness of specialists in terms of their level of competence. The effectiveness of the teaching process at a university, including medical, is determined not only by a high level of competence in the field of medical knowledge, but also by the possession of elements of communicative competence - one of the general competencies on the basis of which the

professional competence of a teacher who teaches a future specialist is built, for this it is necessary to form skills student-oriented, interactive, project-based forms of education, taking into account the normative model of requirements that reflect the professional pedagogical competence of the teacher [26, 29].

Teachers of the higher medical school are a special category of teachers with specific functions, conditions and methods of work, qualification and personal characteristics. Today, in the context of the reform of higher education, the responsibility of teachers of medical universities for the results of their work is increasing, so it becomes important to ensure that the qualifications of teachers correspond to the competency-based approach in higher professional education in the context of its continuity. This becomes possible if the modular model of the educational process is used, where the ratio of the teaching load changes in the direction of increasing the independent work of students with educational and methodological literature and electronic educational resources, this approach assumes close interaction between the student and the teacher, focused on the acquisition of professional skills (competencies). Improving higher medical education involves following the basic principles of the Bologna Declaration, according to which each teacher of a medical university must additionally have a pedagogical education, on the organizational and pedagogical foundations of teaching at a medical university, didactic foundations for the development and application of modern teaching technologies in a medical university under the program "Teacher of Higher Education" (Order of the Ministry of Education of the Russian Federation "On the introduction of State requirements for the minimum content and level of training for obtaining additional qualifications" Teacher of higher education ". The principle of modular construction and compatibility of programs allows us to solve the problem of the appropriateness of sufficiency and selectivity in the training of teachers of medical universities of different skill levels, in determining the volume, content and labor intensity of the recommended educational program [22, 26, 30].

Vocational education, its main goal is the implementation of the professional component of personality development. The main claim of employers to professional educational institutions today is the isolation of the acquired knowledge from practice, which is manifested by the inability to handle modern equipment, in psychological unpreparedness for the realities of production. Employers - chief doctors - often reproach universities for "theorized training", but at the same time they themselves formally approach the conduct of

industrial practices. The employer must participate in the organization and conduct of production practices, participation in the final certification. I would like employers to express their comments and complaints about the quality of training in the educational process. Instead of purposefully "surviving" departments from departments and hospitals, it is necessary to fix them in medical institutions. In addition to developing competencies, the organization of internships plays an important role in cooperation with employers. An adequate and versatile assessment of the quality of vocational education by the employer can be given only after the graduate (specialist) is able to prove himself in practice, at the workplace, in a particular medical institution. Obviously, both sides of the social partnership will benefit from such interaction, the employer will receive a specialist with the necessary qualifications, the educational institution has the opportunity to train a specialist who is in demand on the labor market, which will significantly increase the prestige and authority of the educational institution [8].

Important in the development of higher medical education in Russia is the integration of higher education into the European educational space, which is expressed in the implementation of educational standards of the third generation, the introduction of innovative approaches to the psychological and pedagogical support of the educational process and the methodological readiness of the teaching staff for this. The task is to increase the level of competence of medical teachers in terms of mastering innovative teaching methods and the readiness to implement them in a real pedagogical process [4]. IN AND. Andreev [2] proposes to include knowledge of basic psychological and pedagogical concepts in the model; regularities of the educational process and didactic principles; modern theories and technologies of education; requirements for the preparation and effective implementation of various forms of organization of training; to teach methodology and methodological principles of teaching; methods of pedagogical research. The degree of formation of competencies, proposed in the model of professional competence of a teacher, will ensure the most complete development of individual abilities and personal qualities of students. The federal state educational standard shifts the emphasis of the main educational program from the content side of the disciplines, expressed through knowledge, skills and abilities (what the teacher should teach), to the expected results, expressed in competencies (what the specialist should be able to do after successfully completing the discipline). This requires an increase in the variety of educational technologies used, mainly of an active

and interactive type [1]. Thus, it is supposed to transform the organization of the educational process and the structure of classes. The roles of students and teachers in the educational process are changing. Passive listeners should become active participants in the educational process, while teachers should become "mentors and guides". The above indicated leads to a change in the content and structure of the functions and competencies of university teachers [5].

A new educational paradigm from a reproductive-performing to a cultural-creative model allows a person in the 21st century to study in a humanistically oriented pedagogical space, exercising his right to design the content of education and his own pace of learning at individual stages. The focus of the teacher's attention is the personality of the student, his cognitive activity, the ability to learn and the "taste" for independent knowledge are instilled. With the help of integrated teaching of disciplines, the motivation of the cognitive process, the intensification of the process of developing professional competencies, the solution of the same issue with a significant increase in the independence of the student are achieved [13].

A social paradigm based on knowledge is currently being formed. Awareness of the importance of the socio-economic potential of education has led to the ideology and practice of lifelong learning. The goals and objectives of such training were proclaimed in 1999 in the Cologne Charter at the G8 summit. "Continuing education should become the main political program of civil society. The progress and prospects for the implementation of the idea of continuous education in the EU member states are reflected in the project "Education and Training 2020" [24, 25].

Today we have to admit that the system of professional medical education that has developed in the country is characterized by a number of weaknesses [10]: the discrepancy between the quality of training specialists and modern requirements, the lack of an integrated system of professional training in the conditions of "university-real clinical practice", the lack of external technology standardized for practical healthcare tasks assessing the quality of vocational education.

A weak link in domestic education is additional (postgraduate) education - education for adults, obtained in various forms of retraining and additional education. The traditional model of training, when employees acquire the necessary knowledge and skills during the period of employment, is inadequate to the realities of modern society. Russia's transition to continuous education

requires the development of a special approach to the formation of the content, organization and control of the results of education. The development of such an approach is hampered by the lack of a modern national system of qualifications, a mechanism for the formation of modern standard requirements for a profession and standard technologies for each specialty. The transition to lifelong learning requires a change in the educational management system and its resource support [10, 14, 36].

The ideological and methodological prerequisites for the concept of lifelong education include the research of F. Coombs, the conclusions of the report of the International Commission of UNESCO on changing the paradigm of modern education [20, 25]. The formation of the basic foundations of a modern system of continuous education involves the creation of conditions for solving interrelated tasks: the development of a competitive educational environment and its saturation with a variety of educational services, the creation of an infrastructure for continuous education, the introduction of modern learning technologies, new financial mechanisms. Teaching methods rooted in the system of additional professional education do not ensure the formation of students' abilities for practical actions in the changed economic conditions, since they are based on traditional lecture teaching methods, therefore, the problem of the transition of continuous professional education to new teaching technologies (educational modules, project-based teaching methods) must be solved. , internships, distance learning, etc.), which will increase the effectiveness of education [1, 23, 30]. Distance learning, as a kind of telecommunication type of education, is an innovative component in the medical industry, includes distance technologies and is implemented by means of Internet technologies or other computer tools that provide interactivity. Any training event conducted using distance learning technologies can be assessed in credits (credit units). A promising task of the university is the development and implementation of high technologies in scientific, pedagogical and clinical activities at all stages of the professional education of doctors [9]. In the educational programs of postgraduate professional education, a modular principle for constructing the educational process is formulated, as well as recommendations for organizing the accounting of the teaching load in credit units as a measure of the achievement by students of certain professional competencies. The credit-module system becomes not only the basis for the training of a highly qualified specialist, but also a long-term prospect for improving the quality of this

process, an important component of the continuous professional development of a doctor [19].

The specifics of the organization of training is determined by the characteristics of the contingent of students, as well as the goals, content and conditions of training. According to these parameters, training at the pre-university and postgraduate stages differs. Students in the postgraduate segment of the educational services sector are classified as adult learners. The main goal of their education is to meet specific and individualized educational needs, focused on acquiring the competencies necessary to improve their social roles and to develop their own personality. The content is clearly determined by the specific area of practice. Specific conditions are characterized by a compressed time budget, short training periods and, in some cases, a combination of difficult and responsible professional duties. These parameters require the organization of training for specialists on andragogical principles, which are increasingly and widely used at the level of postgraduate and additional professional education. At the same time, the main problem of teachers in the field of postgraduate and additional professional education in organizing training on andragogical principles is the insufficient level of competence, i.e. insufficient level of skills to perform the actions and functions of a specialist teaching adults based on knowledge, skills, personal qualities and value orientations. Solving this problem is the key to solving other problems of organizing training on andragogical principles in the field of postgraduate and additional professional education [15, 31].

The problem of continuous medical education methodologically goes back to Hippocrates, who affirmed the infinity of improving the art of healing. A person who has chosen the profession of a doctor is doomed to eternal learning, he must be a competent person [18]. Continuing medical education is a process that includes the assessment of a doctor's professional practice with the acquisition of communications and competencies. Until now, the traditional postgraduate continuing professional education in Russia as a system of obtaining knowledge has lagged behind the real needs of modern medical science and the requirements of international medical practice, so there is a need for significant changes in this area. The main reasons for the decline in the quality of medical education include the low level of equipment of the educational process, the decrease in the educational level, the insufficient clinical training of the doctor, and the low motivation of the doctor to improve his professional level [17, 18, 22, 36].

Objective indicators of the quality and safety of medical care are 2 times worse than in developed countries. Dissatisfaction of patients (more than 2/3) with the quality and availability of medical care. Increasing the volume of medical information and the speed of its update. Introduction into practice of new complex medical technologies, the application of which requires additional knowledge and skills. The emergence of new highly efficient information, telecommunication and distance technologies, the introduction of which into the practice of medical education reduces costs and provides additional opportunities for objectifying knowledge [27].

Conclusion

At the present stage in the healthcare system, not just “qualified professionals” in a narrow sense, but creative individuals who are able to acquire the necessary competencies and, on their basis, new methods of training other specialists, should be quoted. Creative pedagogical individuality is important, which is always mediated by the personal qualities of the teacher, because creative originality is the highest characteristic of a teacher. Russia should enter the Bologna process without destroying the foundations of its education, but developing them, while further improving the system of national medical education, taking into account educational standards. Ensuring the innovative nature of medical education of a qualitatively new level, taking into account modern requirements and global trends with the formation of a system of continuous education as a tool for professional development, should become a strategic goal, and the implementation of this goal, as rightly noted by P.V. Glybochko [10], involves the solution of strategic directions: the introduction of a competency-based approach, the development of the variability of educational programs using new educational technologies, the introduction of effective high-quality training and retraining of specialists based on the experience of leading institutions, the formation of a system of external independent certification of professional competencies and accreditation of specialists, the creation a system of continuous professional development based on the principles of an open educational space.

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